

Coupling of the VALKIN Neutronic code (Diffusion and Transport) with the PATHS Thermal-Hydraulic code for Nuclear Reactor Simulations

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ABSTRACT

This work presents a steady-state neutronic-thermal-hydraulic coupling methodology between the neutronic code VALKIN-FVM and the thermal-hydraulic code PATHS, including two neutronic solver options within a unified framework: diffusion (VALKIN-FVM) and Sn transport (VALKIN-FVM-Sn). Coupling is performed through an iterative scheme in which PATHS provides fuel temperature and coolant density (and boron concentration when applicable) to update group constants, while VALKIN returns the three-dimensional power distribution to PATHS. Iterations proceed until convergence of the neutronic and thermal-hydraulic fields is achieved.

The coupling is verified through code-to-code comparisons against the reference system PARCS and its integrated PATHS module, using k-effective and power distribution as primary quantities of interest. Very good agreement is obtained for the diffusion option. The Sn option shows higher deviations in the present work, mainly driven by transport consistent cross-section processing that is currently under refinement. However, the coupled solutions remain stable and within acceptance criteria.

The main contribution of this work is the integration of a transport code (VALKIN-FVM-Sn) within coupled neutronic-thermal-hydraulic framework, providing a foundation for high-fidelity simulations of advanced reactor concepts. Future research will focus on refining transport cross-section processing, extending the methodology to transient analyses, and incorporating depletion capabilities into VALKIN-FVM and VALKIN-FVM-Sn to enable detailed cycle-follow analyses throughout the reactor operation, similar to those available in PARCS.

Keywords: VALKIN-FVM-Sn, neutronic, thermal-hydraulic, PATHS, PARCS, diffusion, transport.

1. INTRODUCTION

Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) represent a strategic option for the future of nuclear energy due to their safety features, modular design and ability to operate in decentralized environments. Their analysis and design require advanced computational methodologies capable of accurately simulating the interaction between neutronic and thermal-hydraulic phenomena, given the strong interdependence between these two domains [1]. In this paper, the proposed methodology is demonstrated and verified on a PWR-KWU full-core model as a representative reference case.

Neutronic behavior governs the spatial power distribution within the core, which directly influences coolant density, fuel temperature, and boron concentration. These thermal-hydraulic variations, in turn, modify cross sections, affecting neutron flux and reactivity feedback [2].

Traditional approaches often rely on diffusion-based neutronic solvers coupled with thermal-hydraulic models to reduce computational cost. However, diffusion approximations assume isotropic flux and spatial gradients, limiting accuracy in regions with more heterogeneities or near boundaries. Transport-based methods, such as discrete ordinates (Sn), provide higher fidelity by resolving angular flux dependence, but at the expense of increased computational requirements.

In this context, this work introduces the coupling of VALKIN-FVM code -in both diffusion and transport versions- with the PATHS (PARCS Advanced Thermal-Hydraulic Solver). The proposed coupling allows bidirectional exchange of key variables such as fuel temperature, moderator density and power distribution, providing a realistic interpretation of core behavior under varying conditions.

The objectives of this work are to develop and implement the VALKIN-FVM/PATHS steady-state coupling methodology for both diffusion (VALKIN-FVM) and transport (VALKIN-FVM-Sn) solvers, and to verify the coupled implementation through code-to-code comparisons against the reference workflow PARCS (diffusion)/PATHS using k_{eff} and power distributions as the primary quantities of interest.

Finally, the motivation for implementing transport-based coupling lies in the fact that, while diffusion solvers have proven effective for conventional reactors, such as PWRs, BWRs..., their approximations may not be sufficiently accurate for SMRs due to their compact geometry and other characteristics. Therefore, having transport methods becomes valuable to ensure reliable simulations for next-generation reactor designs.

2. CODES DESCRIPTION

2.1. VALKIN-FVM

VALKIN-FVM is a deterministic reactor physics code for multigroup neutron diffusion and discrete ordinates transport calculations. The governing equations are spatially discretized with the Finite Volume Method (FVM), enabling calculations on structured and unstructured meshes for complex geometries. For transport, the angular dependence is treated with the Discrete Ordinates (Sn) method and different quadrature options are available. [3-8].

The code produces flux and power distributions and exports results in ASCII and VTK formats for post-processing and visualization.

In this work, VALKIN-FVM-Sn calculations use a Gauss-Legendre product quadrature and an angular order of $S_n=3$ for all the transport results reported in the paper.

2.2. PARCS

PARCS is a three-dimensional reactor core simulator developed to perform steady-state and transient neutronic calculations. It solves the multigroup neutron diffusion equation and, optionally, low-order transport approximations in cartesian or hexagonal geometries. The code supports eigenvalues searches, depletions analysis, pin power reconstruction, and kinetics calculations with delayed neutron treatment [9]. It is widely used for licensing and safety analyses.

In the present study, PARCS calculations are performed using the diffusion solver, the SP3 solver is not used for the results discussed in the following sections.

2.3. PATHS Thermal-Hydraulic code

The PATHS code (PARCS Advanced Thermal Hydraulic Solver) is a thermal-hydraulic solver that can operate either independently, using a predefined power distribution, or coupled with a neutronics code to obtain a converged neutronics-thermal-hydraulic solution.

It employs a drift-flux model with four simplified equations and resolution algorithms that significantly reduce executions time. This computational efficiency makes PATHS particularly advantageous in applications requiring a one-to-one mapping of a thermal-hydraulic channel for each fuel assembly, and in the repetitive resolution of the steady-state thermal-hydraulic conditions of the core during the equilibrium cycle search [10].

3. MODEL

A Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) KWU with 177 fuel assemblies arranged in a 17x17 lattice and 34 axial levels is studied. The first axial level represents the lower reflector, while the last corresponds to the upper reflector.

The effective cross sections used were generated using the SIMTAB methodology [11], developed jointly by Universitat Politècnica de València and Iberdrola. The resulting macroscopic cross sections are parametrized as functions of fuel temperature and moderator density and are stored in two files, *nemtab* and *nemtabr*, in NEMTAB format. All simulations were performed with the control rods fully withdrawn.

In this work, a structured 2x2x2 mesh composed of 8 identical parallelepipeds is employed. This choice provides uniform control over the discretization and maintains a moderate computational cost, which is appropriate for the objectives of study.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Steady-State Verification

This section presents the steady-state verification of the VALKIN-FVM code in both diffusion (VALKIN-FVM) and transport (VALKIN-FVM-Sn) modes against the reference code PARCS, which is operated in diffusion mode. The objective is to ensure consistency in standalone neutronic predictions (k -effective and power distributions) prior to introducing thermal-hydraulic feedback in the coupled simulations with PATHS presented in Section 4.2.

4.1.1. Diffusion Solver (VALKIN-FVM)

Two approaches are analysed:

- Case 1: VALKIN-FVM read the tabulated libraries NEMTAB/NEMTABR and obtains macroscopic group constant by interpolations as a function of the local feedback variables. The interpolations is driven by the node-wise moderator density and fuel temperature fields provided in the DENS and TFUS files. In this case, control rods are withdrawn. The same core state is simulated with PARCS for reference.
- Case 2: The same steady-state PARCS calculation as in Case 1 (using the node-wise TFUS/DENS fields and the underlying NEMTAB/NEMTABR libraries) is first performed. From this PARCS run, we export the macroscopic multigroup constants actually used in the calculation (diffusion coefficients, absorption, fission and nu-fission cross sections, scattering matrix, and fission spectrum by energy group) per neutronic composition/node into an xsecfile. We then re-run PARCS using this xsecfile to confirm that the exported dataset reproduces the original PARCS solution. Finally, the same xsecfile is provided to VALKIN-FVM, so that both codes use an identical macroscopic dataset and remaining differences can be attributed primarily to solver effects rather than cross-sections processing.

Table I summarizes the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) for both cases. When using NEMTAB (case 1), the deviation from PARCS is 19.4 pcm, while with *xsecfile* (case 2) the deviation decreases to 17.3 pcm. In both cases, the error is within acceptable limits.

Table I. Effective multiplication factor in steady-state (PARCS vs VALKIN-FVM).

Case	k_{eff} PARCS	k_{eff} VALKIN-FVM	Deviation (pcm)
NEMTAB	0.999151	0.999345	19.4
xsecfile	0.999151	0.999324	17.3

Figure 1 shows the radial power error map for Case 1, with a global RMS of 1.059%, while Figure 2 (Case 2) shows an RMS of 0.979% demonstrating strong consistency between VALKIN-FVM and PARCS when identical cross sections are used.

Figure 1. Radial power error map PARCS vs VALKIN-FVM (NEMTAB).

Figure 2. Radial power error map PARCS vs VALKIN-FVM (xsecfile).

Figure 3 compares axial power profiles, where there is a high degree of agreement between VALKIN-FVM and PARCS, with minimal differences across the core.

Figure 3. Axial Power Profile comparison PARCS vs VALKIN-FVM.

These results confirm that the diffusion solver provides accurate predictions under steady-state conditions, validating its implementation.

4.1.2. Transport Solver (VALKIN-FVM-Sn)

The same cases were simulated using the transport solver VALKIN-FVM-Sn. All VALKIN-FVM-Sn results shown in this section were obtained with Sn=3 using a Gauss-Legendre product quadrature.

Table II shows that when using NEMTAB, the k_{eff} deviation from PARCS is 45.6 pcm, while with *xsecfile* the error slightly decreases to 44.5 pcm. Although these values remain within acceptable limits, they are notably higher than those obtained with diffusion.

Table II. Effective multiplication factor in steady-state (PARCS vs VALKIN-FVM-Sn).

Case	k_{eff} PARCS	k_{eff} VALKIN-FVM-Sn	Deviation (pcm)
NEMTAB	0.999151	0.999607	45.6
xsecfile	0.999151	0.999596	44.5

Regarding radial power distribution, Figure 4 (NEMTAB) shows a global RMS of 6.588%, and Figure 5 (*xsecfile*) exhibits a similar RMS of 6.583%.

Figure 4. Radial power error map PARCS vs VALKIN-FVM-Sn (NEMTAB).

Figure 5. Radial power error map PARCS vs VALKIN-FVM-Sn (*xsecfile*).

Figure 6 compares axial power profiles, revealing slight deviations in the central area of the core and near the core boundaries.

Figure 6. Axial Power Profile comparison PARCS vs VALKIN-FVM-Sn.

Although the deviations observed in transport simulations are higher than those obtained with diffusion, this is mainly because the cross-section set for transport calculations is still under optimization. Nevertheless, all results remain within acceptable limits, which allows us to proceed coupling both solvers VALKIN-FVM and VALKIN-FVM-Sn with the PATHS thermal-hydraulic model.

4.2. Coupling Verification

This section presents the results of the coupled simulations between the neutronic solvers VALKIN-FVM (diffusion) and VALKIN-FVM-Sn (transport) coupled with the thermal-hydraulic solver PATHS.

Figure 7. Steady-state VALKIN-PATHS coupling workflow.

Figure 7 summarizes the steady-state iterative coupling between VALKIN-FVM (diffusion)/ VALKIN-FVM-Sn (transport) and PATHS. The iteration starts from an initial thermal-hydraulic state (TFUS and DENS, and boron density when applicable). Given these feedback variables, the neutronic code updates the macroscopic group constants by interpolating the pre-tabulated libraries NEMTAB/NEMTABR at node level and solves the neutronic eigenvalue problem to obtain k_{eff} and the three-dimensional power distribution $P(x,y,z)$. The power field is then mapped to the corresponding thermal-hydraulic channels and transferred to PATHS, which computes an updated steady-state thermal-hydraulic solution and returns new DENS and TFUS values to VALKIN. This exchange is

repeated until simultaneous convergence is achieved in both domains: (i) thermal-hydraulic convergence reported by PATHS (THconv flag) and (ii) neutronic convergence based on the relative change in eigenvalue, $\Delta k_{eff} \leq 10^{-5}$, together with stability of the power distribution within predefined tolerances.

In the coupled VALKIN-PATHS iterations, macroscopic cross sections are updated at each iteration by interpolating the tabulated libraries NEMTAB/NEMTABR using the current fuel temperatures and moderator densities returned by PATHS. Therefore, the coupling workflow in Figure 7 applies to the NEMTAB/NEMTABR route (Case 1). The xsecfile approach (Case 2) is used only for code-to-code verification under a prescribed steady-state case, where node-wise macroscopic constants are fixed and no iterative cross-section update with PATHS is performed; hence it does not represent the feedback-driven coupling procedure.

4.2.1. VALKIN-FVM with PATHS

The first coupling involves the diffusion solver VALKIN-FVM integrated with PATHS. The simulation uses a NEMTAB file for cross sections and the DENS and TFUS files for moderator densities and fuel temperatures, respectively.

Table III summarizes the k_{eff} obtained with PARCS/PATHS and VALKIN-FVM/PATHS. The deviation is 17.2 pcm, which is well within acceptable limits for steady-state coupled calculations.

Table III. Effective multiplication factor in coupling (PARCS/PATHS vs VALKIN-FVM/PATHS).

k_{eff} PARCS/PATHS	k_{eff} VALKIN-FVM/PATHS	Deviation (pcm)
1.002262	1.002434	17.2

Figure 8 shows the radial power error map, with a global RMS of 0.76%, while Figure 9 compares axial power profiles, demonstrating strong agreement between the two coupled solutions.

Figure 8. Radial power error map PARCS/PATHS vs VALKIN-FVM/PATHS.

Figure 9. Axial Power Profile comparison PARCS/PATHS vs VALKIN-FVM/PATHS.

These results confirm that the diffusion-based coupling provides accurate predictions under steady-state conditions, validating the integration of VALKIN-FVM with PATHS.

4.2.2. VALKIN-FVM-Sn with PATHS

The second coupling case involves the transport solver VALKIN-FVM-Sn integrated with PATHS. The same procedure described in sections 4.2.1 is applied. In this case, the comparison focuses on the results obtained from PARCS/PATHS and VALKIN-FVM-Sn/PATHS simulations. While PARCS uses diffusion-based cross sections and VALKIN-FVM-Sn employs transport-based cross sections, differences are expected to be slightly larger due to the different approaches used. Nevertheless, the primary objective is to validate the coupling methodology and ensure that the integrated solutions remain within acceptable limits.

Table IV presents the k_{eff} comparison between PARCS/PATHS and VALKIN-FVM-Sn/PATHS, obtaining a deviation of 2.7 pcm.

Table IV. Effective multiplication factor in coupling (PARCS/PATHS vs VALKIN-FVM-Sn/PATHS).

k_{eff} PARCS/PATHS	k_{eff} VALKIN-FVM-Sn/PATHS	Deviation (pcm)
1.002262	1.002289	2.7

Figure 10 presents the radial power error map, with an RMS of 5.34%, and Figure 11 compares axial power profiles, where some deviations appear around the axial nodes of the core.

Figure 10. Radial power error map PARCS/PATHS vs VALKIN-FVM-Sn/PATHS.

Figure 11. Axial Power Profile comparison PARCS/PATHS vs VALKIN-FVM-Sn/PATHS.

Although the deviations observed in transport-based coupling are higher than those obtained with diffusion, this is primarily due to the ongoing optimizations of the cross-section set for transport calculations. Nevertheless, the results remain within acceptable limits, enabling us to confidently proceed with further analyses and refinements.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The verification and coupling results presented in this work demonstrate that the VALKIN-FVM diffusion solver and the VALKIN-FVM-Sn transport solver can be successfully integrated with the PATHS thermal-hydraulic code. Under steady-state conditions, diffusion-based coupling achieved excellent agreement with the reference PARCS/PATHS solution. Transport-based coupling exhibited slightly higher discrepancies, primarily due to the ongoing optimization of the cross sections.

These findings establish a solid foundation for future work. The goal of this development is to apply the integrated coupling code to SMRs, where transport methods are expected to provide superior accuracy compared to diffusion approximations due to the compact geometry and stronger heterogeneities of SMR cores.

Future efforts will focus on refining cross-section generation for transport calculations, extending the methodology to transient scenarios.

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